

Some new insect pests of rice in Uttar Pradesh, India

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Surveys conducted during 1981-84 revealed the presence of several insect pests not previously reported on upland rice in the hills of Uttar Pradesh (see table). Most of these pests have

recorded low economic loss, but their occurrence indicates that they could become serious pests under favorable climatic conditions.

Of the insects found, shootfly caused 22-25% deadhearts in the nursery in 1983. Small grasshoppers were abundant throughout the 1984 season. Other insects remained at a low level.

The Commonwealth Institute of Entomology, London, confirmed the insect identification. *S*

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Insect and year when first recorded	Order:Family	Damage
Horned caterpillar <i>Melanitis leda</i> Linnaeus 1981 ^a	Lepidoptera:Satyridae	Larvae feed on leaf blade.
Tussock caterpillar <i>Euproctis</i> sp. probably <i>Virguncula</i> Walker 1981	Lepidoptera:Lymantriidae	Larvae are defoliators.
Bombay locust <i>Patanga succincta</i> (Linnaeus) 1982	Orthoptera:Acrididae	Nymph and adults feed on leaves.
Small grasshopper <i>Oxya japonica japonica</i> (Thunberg) 1982	Orthoptera:Acrididae	Nymphs and adults feed on leaves.
Aphid <i>Hysteroneura setariae</i> (Thomas) 1982	Homoptera:Aphididae	Feeds on shoots and developing panicles.
Green leafhopper <i>Nephotettix nigropictus</i> (Stal.) 1981	Homoptera:Cicadellidae	Nymphs and adults suck sap from leaves.
Leafhopper <i>Psammodettix striatus</i> (Linne) 1981	Homoptera:Cicadellidae	Nymphs and adults suck sap from leaves in nursery seedlings.
Leaf fly <i>Oscinella</i> sp. 1981	Diptera:Chloropidae	Larvae cause whitish hollow outgrowths of interval leaf.
Earwig <i>Elaunon bipartitus</i> (Kirby) 1981	Dermaptera:Forficulidae	Adults observed on panicles.
Flea beetle <i>Chaetocnema basalis</i> (Baly) 1982	Coleoptera:Chrysomelidae	Adults feed on leaves by biting holes in them.
Shootfly <i>Atherigona oryzae</i> Mall. 1983	Diptera:Muscidae	Maggots feed on central shoot of seedlings.
Pollen beetle <i>Chiloloba acuta</i> (Wiedemann) 1982	Coleoptera:Scarabaeidae	Adults are observed as pollen feeders.

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Predators of rice caseworm

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The leaf tube constructed by rice caseworm *Nymphula depunctalis* protects the larvae from natural enemies. Larval parasitization is always below 5%. The role of aquatic predators was assessed in greenhouse trials.

Caseworm larvae caged in potted plants immersed in water were offered as prey to a range of aquatic insects collected from reservoirs, canals, and ricefields. Two predatory groups were revealed. The larvae of *Sternolophus rufipes* (Fabricius), a hydrophilid, stalk caseworm larvae underwater and seize them as they stretch out of their protective cases while swimming. Sometimes the predator entered the case to locate the caseworm. The larva of *Cybister tripunctatus orientalis* Gschwendtner, a dytiscid, holds onto a submerged object waiting for prey to swim overhead. It rises quickly to the surface and seizes the outstretched caseworm larva. Younger dytiscids enter the case while older ones seize the case with powerful, sickle-shaped mandibles, forcing the caseworm larvae out.

Single dytiscid or hydrophilid larvae that were offered caseworm larvae of a range of ages in no-choice tests showed preference for older prey (see table).

Capacity of aquatic beetle larvae to prey on rice caseworm larvae in no-choice tests. IIRRI greenhouse, 1984.

Caseworm larval instar	Caseworm larvae consumed (no./d)		
	Hydrophilid ^a instar IV	Dytiscid ^b	
		Instar II	Instar IV
I	2.2 c	4.8 b	4.0 b
II	2.8 bc	4.8 b	4.0 b
III	4.5 ab	8.4 ab	9.0 ab
IV	5.2 ab	10.0 ab	10.8 a
V	6.7 a	11.6 a	11.4 a

^aAv of 5 replications; single predator larva offered 15 prey. ^bAv of 6 replications; single predator larva offered 25 prey.